

Navigating Problematic Bauhaus Inheritances:

Critiques, Implications, and Questions from the Bauhaus of the Seas NEB Lighthouse

Nicholas Torretta

ITI/LARSyS, IST-U. Lisbon Portugal, nunojnunes@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Mariana Pestana

ITI/LARSyS, IST-U. Lisbon Portugal, marianapestana@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Frederico Duarte

ITI/LARSyS, IST-U. Lisbon Portugal, frederico.duarte@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Cristiano Pedroso-Roussado

ITI/LARSyS, IST-U. Lisbon Portugal, marianapestana@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Luisa Metello Seixas

ITI/LARSyS, IST-U. Lisbon Portugal, marianapestana@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Nuno Jardim Nunes

ITI/LARSyS, IST-U. Lisbon Portugal, marianapestana@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

In 2020, Europe announced the New European Bauhaus (NEB). While the initiative intends to achieve EU sustainability goals, framing it under the name of the Bauhaus brings various challenges and issues to the fore. In this article, we analyze the critiques of the original Bauhaus and the NEB to understand the challenges that the NEB lighthouse project Bauhaus of the Seas Sails (BoSS) inherits by adhering to the Bauhaus vision and name. We unveil the problematic dynamics of Eurocentric modernity's myths of universalism and better living through technology and on the Bauhaus's and NEB's position in global power structures. Instead of assuming a tabula rasa approach and replicating problematic structures unknowingly, we bring these three aspects to BoSS to find questions as orientation points to help steer away from problematic aspects inherited by reanimating the Bauhaus name and its legacy.

Additional Keywords and Phrases: Bauhaus, New European Bauhaus, decolonial, criticality, regenerative design

1 INTRODUCTION

In 2020, European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen called for a new design movement to respond to the challenges of the twenty-first century. She named this vision the New European Bauhaus (NEB).ⁱ NEB is framed as a “renovation wave” aiming at implementing the European sustainability goals—the European Green Deal—based on three pillars: sustainability, social inclusion, and beauty.ⁱⁱ In response to this call for action, the Portuguese ministers of culture and science, technology and higher education gathered a group of experts and proposed a mobilization around water bodies.ⁱⁱⁱ Called Bauhaus of the Seas, the proposal was presented to the Portuguese government and the EC in early 2021 in the form of a manifesto.^{iv} This manifesto evolved into an international conversation leading to an international consortium and the Bauhaus of the Seas (BoS) project.^v BoS was one of the first six projects selected as “lighthouse demonstrators” of the NEB. The project started in January 2023, proposing a perspective from the sea to the continent to rethink relations to bodies of water. In practice, BoS project aims at exploring possibilities for regenerative relations to water bodies and involving more-than-humans such process (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: The Bauhaus of the Seas Approach

Reanimating the name of the Bauhaus comes with challenges since it is now over 100 years since the original Bauhaus school was founded. We face new challenges in contemporary environmental, social, cultural, and political contexts. To understand where we are and how the NEB frame can influence BoS, we need to understand what we inherit from the NEB and the original Bauhaus. In this article, we explore the critiques surrounding the original Bauhaus and the NEB to achieve a productive but critical stance for BoS. In analyzing ways to act in such inheritance, we may think in terms of ethics of probability versus ethics of possibility.^{vi} Ethics of probability are ways of thinking and doing that are a continuation of structures and established systems of thought based on “diagnosis, counting and accounting.”^{vii} Nevertheless, the ethics of possibility are ways of thinking and acting fueled by hope and aspiration. Ethics of possibility stems from informed, creative, and critical citizenship, which “increase the horizons of hope.”^{viii} Arjun Appadurai claims that ethics of possibility “can offer a more inclusive platform for improving the planetary equality of life and can accommodate a plurality of visions of the good life.”^{ix}

Under the NEB, we may be conscripted to act in the ethics of probability should we fail to critically address the history and legacy of the Bauhaus and the NEB frame. In doing a review of critiques and assuming a critical stance toward the BoS project, our goal is to move toward the ethics of possibility. If what we need for ethics of possibility is a critical awareness throughout BoS, we may benefit from orientation points to guide us. Daniel C. Wahl argues that to develop regenerative design projects, we may benefit from shifting from searching for right answers to searching for better questions.^x In the next section, we present an overview of the critiques of the original Bauhaus and the NEB. In the last section, we bring these critiques to BoS and outline questions that may serve as orientation points for an ethics of possibility.

2 OVERVIEW OF CRITIQUES

The Original Bauhaus and the NEB have been widely criticized, here we overview such critiques to gather issues that may be relevant for BoS and other projects dealing with the inheritances of the Bauhaus and the NEB frame.

2.1 The Original Bauhaus School

Bauhaus futures must grapple with problematic Bauhaus histories, particularly histories that exclude the bulk of the world’s people from having design in any meaningful way.^{xi}

The legacy of the Bauhaus is well known. Over its short existence from 1919 to 1933, the German school became a major reference for design worldwide. Its history and legacy have been analyzed, reinterpreted, and critiqued from various perspectives. For example, Ramia Mazé presents a feminist critique of the Bauhaus where she highlights how the school was not egalitarian, privileging men over women and even denying women to join certain programs.^{xii} From a racial perspective, Elizabeth Chin showed how the Bauhaus was built on the exploitation and exclusion of others.^{xiii} She argues that the products designed in the Bauhaus, while aimed toward a “universal mankind,” relied on the exploitation of other places and people, especially in and from regions colonized by European empires. To explain Chin’s argument, we can bring in Renata M. Leitão’s work on revealing the myths of Eurocentric modernity in design.^{xiv} Leitão argues that Eurocentric modernity created a view of Europe as the main reference, the neutral culture, while posing non-Western cultures as the underdeveloped “exotic other.” Similarly, Elizabeth Tunstall problematized how the Bauhaus was responsible for spreading modernist principles of white supremacy through the idea of the “universal man”:

The Bauhaus’s “universal man” for whom they were designing was the working white man. They sought to protect his war-traumatized body and spirit through the economizing of space and the meaningfulness of satisfactory and productive work. Design practices that draw their origin stories from the modernist project thus perpetuate the biases of the supremacy of white bodies and cultural values. . . . The Bauhaus was just drawing upon earlier foundations of the modernist project in design.^{xv}

Tunstall highlights how the oppressive aspects of the Bauhaus are the expression of a European movement in society and culture that became known as Eurocentric modernity. To better ground this argument, we need to unpack the link between the Bauhaus and Eurocentric modernity.

2.2 Eurocentric Modernity, the Bauhaus, and Colonization

Eurocentric modernity is widely considered as a worldview created in Europe that positioned Europe at the top of the global hierarchy and that has affected the world far beyond its borders.^{xvi} In Europe, as Enrique Dussel argues, modernity was a way out of feudal life and imposed feudal hierarchies.^{xvii} Modernity was also a way to develop Western science to achieve intellectual freedom from religious institutions. However, Eurocentric modernity came with an understanding of humans as separate from nature and, consequently, the understanding of nature as something to be exploited for the benefit of man.^{xviii} As Hicham Khalidi and Rolando Vázquez argue:

The losses of cultural diversity and biodiversity arrived hand in hand with modernity. The Western project of civilization was forged through Eurocentrism and anthropocentrism. While Eurocentrism has caused the demise of other cultures, of other worlds of meaning, anthropocentrism has meant the exploitation of Earth. Earth has become an Other to the human.^{xix}

Walter Mignolo argues for always writing *modern* together with *colonial* (moder/colonial) as Eurocentric modernity was built on the exploitation of other places, especially through colonization.^{xx} Leitão highlights that Eurocentric

modernity/coloniality came to its epitome in the Industrial Revolution,^{xxi} which increased Europe's reliance on the raw materials extracted or produced in European colonies, mostly based on enslaved labor.^{xxii} Even after the process of independence of several nations from their European colonizers, various authors argue that the center-periphery power relation remains present. Aníbal Quijano calls this remaining power relation "coloniality," which stands for a global power dynamic that poses Europe and, since World War II the United States, as the center of the world and the rest as the periphery.^{xxiii} Coloniality does not happen through political control but through the imposition of life aspirations and standards of living created in the center (EU-US) onto the periphery as the correct/normal way of living that should be pursued everywhere.^{xxiv} Hence, Eurocentric modernity and the dynamics of coloniality reproduce a notion of universalism that is grounded on the worldview that superior, hegemonic and elitist European—and in coloniality also US—values and ideas are presumably equally valid everywhere and for everyone. As Khalidi and Vázquez put it: "Eurocentrism, which attributes universal validity to its notions of beauty, enjoyment, and necessity, is inseparable from the exploitation, denigration, and erasure of others' worlds of meaning."^{xxv} Vázquez argues that modernity became Europe's way of "worlding the world"—of creating the world according to European standards and aspirations.^{xxvi} Vázquez and Tunstall argue that design was central to this act of worlding and that the Bauhaus was the protagonist in giving (physical) form to Eurocentric modernity.^{xxvii} Tunstall argues that the values from Eurocentric modernity/coloniality spread via the Bauhaus were not only of the general sense of universalism.^{xxviii} Bauhaus also spread the ideal of better living through technology, a myth that poses technology as the only path for improving life. In her words:

Better living through technology is the propaganda of the modernist project in design. This story that we tell ourselves, . . . through annual design awards, is harmful because technological advances in design, whether of the 1800s or now, only make some lives better. European industrialization in the 1800s went hand in hand with colonization. The better lives through technology were exclusively for European elites and, much later, for European colonial settlers. The vast improvements in lives for European workers and the poor were mostly due to their leaving Europe in mass migrations and the hard-won reforms of the labor movements in places where they settled. The post-World War II white workers of Euro-North America and Euro-Australia experienced—and still experience—the benefits of technology at the direct expense of the land and Indigenous, Black, and other racialized peoples.^{xxix}

We can see that both myths are interconnected, the failure of "better living through technology" in Europe and the former colonies shows that the idea of the "universal man" is also a myth as it relies on exclusion and extractive relations. Through this brief outline, three prominent aspects come to be considered in our search for an ethics of possibility: First, to understand that we are positioned in structures of power, and that what is created in Europe can spread through coloniality. Second, we need to be aware of the myth of universality. Last, if we keep reproducing the myth of better living through technology, we must be critical about who benefits and who is oppressed by the technology and if it leads to improvements in the daily life of all involved in creating, producing, using, and maintaining it. Nevertheless, as Tunstall argues, a critique of Eurocentric modernity/coloniality is not a critique of Europe but a critique of a set of values that has brought the exploitation of nature and other people, a mentality that we must be aware of and move beyond in design and thus in BoS.^{xxx}

2.3 The NEB and Its Critiques

There is a shift in scale and time of our analysis when moving our review to the NEB. The original Bauhaus was a small, short-lived school in Germany, whereas the NEB is a contemporary political initiative of continental magnitude. Furthermore, the NEB is framed to deal with the contemporary environmental crisis in Europe, which is not a local issue

but a global challenge with complex systems of cause and effect. We saw already that the Bauhaus relied on more-than-Europe to come to fruition, especially through colonial power structures. When reviewing the critiques of the NEB, we keep in mind the three aspects highlighted earlier: the myths of universalism and better living through technology, as well as the reliance on colonial power structures and their dynamics.

Perhaps the most well-known critique of the NEB is an open letter sent to the European Commission only weeks after the announcement of the NEB. This letter was led by Hicham Khalidi, director of the Van Eyck Academie.^{xxxix}

The Bauhaus is perceived as the epitome of Modernism, and a critical reading of Modernity inevitably ties it to a past of colonial extractivism and a future of industrial capitalism. The title of your project carries both a strong Western and Eurocentric tone, as well as the legacy of a problematic historical configuration. For these reasons, we feel that this title deals uncritically with such history, and falls short in acknowledging the multiple histories that Europe is made of.^{xxxix}

With different scales, times, and contexts, it would be easy to think that the NEB just carries a name, akin to a brand, merely to give visibility to the new initiative. As Khalidi and Vázquez argue, the act of naming is also an act of “producing monuments.”^{xxxix} The authors highlight the recent global movement of contesting and removing monuments that are symbols of imperialism, colonization, and oppression. They relate the reanimation of the Bauhaus name to the building of a monument that relates to a history of colonial oppression. As stated earlier, various authors stressed that the success of Eurocentric modernity, and consequently the Bauhaus school, depended on colonial power structures. Reanimating the name of the Bauhaus reanimates the myths of Eurocentric modernity/coloniality. Nevertheless, the official documents released by the European Commission stated that several principles of the original Bauhaus were used as a basis for the NEB:

Several features of the historical Bauhaus served as a basis for the vision of the New European Bauhaus. The historical Bauhaus, created in 1919, emerged at a moment of deep transformation—towards the modern societal and industrial era. . . . It quickly became a global cultural movement.^{xxxix}

In contrast to this monumentalizing, even mythical interpretation of the Bauhaus, Tunstall stresses that design in Europe has moved beyond modernism and the Bauhaus tradition.^{xxxix} Bringing back Appadurai, we can look further into the NEB documents and search for whether it is framed on an ethics of probability or if it opens toward an ethics of possibility.^{xxxix} When looking through these documents, we can specifically search for where and how the NEB may reproduce the myths of Eurocentric modernity/coloniality of universalism and better living through technology and where and how the NEB addresses global power structures and dynamics of coloniality. The next section takes a concise overview of the NEB documents released (so far): the 2020 State of the Union speech, the NEB initial communication document, the NEB compass, and the report from the co-design phase of the NEB.^{xxxix}

2.4 NEB Documents: Universalism and Better Living through Technology?

The motto of the NEB is “beautiful, sustainable, together.”^{xxxix} We can start our search by asking: How are these concepts defined? Does the NEB have a universalized notion of these categories, or does it open to plural perspectives? In Box 1 we offer an overview of how each concept is framed throughout the NEB documents.

3 CONCEPTS AND DEFINITIONS

Beautiful: In key NEB-related documents the EU Commission stresses the notion of “beautiful” in relation to style and/or aesthetics. Beautiful is, however, framed differently in each document. In the 2020 State of the Union address, von der Leyen introduced the NEB by affirming: “Every movement has its own look and

feel. And we need to give our systemic change its own distinct aesthetic—to match style with sustainability.”^{xxxix}

In later addresses, documents, and initiatives, the concepts of style and aesthetics are associated with history, architectural heritage and a familiarity with particular objects, authors, or artistic/design styles. In the NEB Compass document, the commission poses three ambitions in relation to the concept of “beautiful”: “to (re)activate the qualities of a given context while contributing to our physical and mental well-being; to connect different places and people and foster a sense of belonging through meaningful collective experiences; and to integrate new enduring cultural and social values through creation.”^{xl}

The NEB Compass document mentions that a place has specific aesthetics and how “beautiful project enables creation, and the collective re-invention of the places, lifestyles, and communities we identify with. It integrates new cultural and social values, notably through the meaningful experience of a broader ‘us’ (including the non-human world).”^{xli}

Sustainable: In the NEB Compass, the concept of “sustainable” is mainly connected to the idea of being in harmony with nature. The document’s driving definition of sustainability is based on the European GreenComp framework: “Sustainability means prioritising the needs of all life forms and of the planet by ensuring that human activity does not exceed planetary boundaries.”^{xlii}

The Compass document mentions that a sustainable project works on the scale of the ecosystem and acknowledges the interconnection between sustainability and mindsets, but keeps the definition grounded on ideas such as circular life cycle, long-lasting products, and environmental impact.^{xliii}

Together: The concept of “together” in the NEB has a major focus on inclusion and co-creation of solutions. It emphasizes the need to focus on vulnerable communities, for example, stating that “new solutions should solve everyday problems and improve the quality of life for all.”^{xliv} The report from the NEB co-design phase has opening toward migration where it states: “For immigrants, it’s important to find back a family dimension for sharing moments with others. Usually these occasions are built around food, and common spaces in shared housing.”^{xlv}

Furthermore, in relation to “together,” the NEB documents argues for the need of connecting globally to spread its values and solutions: “The New European Bauhaus will reach out further beyond European borders over time with the aim of spreading its principles of sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics globally.”^{xlvi}

On closer inspection, none of the concepts of the NEB motto are strictly defined. We may see this vague definition as positive, as it leaves space for interpretation and imagination. Engaging with these terms does not entail dealing with potentially problematic or oppressive definitions. However, we consider these to be rather uncritical definitions. Such an awareness of what is undefined and uncritically defined is necessary if we want to shift to the ethics of possibility and steer away from reproducing problematic inherited mentalities and power structures. This lack of specific definitions and criticality of the NEB has been a target of critiques. Such a lack is seen as a reproduction of the modern/colonial myth of universalism. For instance, Khalidi and Vázquez have argued that the NEB carries a “reduced notion” of Europe, one that sees Europe as a universalized entity, dismissing its diversity.^{xlvii} They argue that such a view is a reflex of Eurocentrism reminiscent of the modern/colonial mentality. In response to this, Khalidi and Vázquez argue that the NEB should overcome the monocultural approach of Eurocentrism as well as the “anthropocentrism that has made of Earth a disposable resource upon which modernity’s dreams were built.”^{xlviii}

Moreover, in the NEB documents, we can see a hint of reanimation of the myth of better living through technology. In the section "together," the NEB states that new solutions should improve everyone's lives. These claims are universalist, implying that solutions can be effective everywhere and to everyone. We see a union of the two myths connecting to the issue of global power structures and the dynamics of coloniality. The European Commission states that the NEB aims to spread its notions of sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics to the rest of the world. As we work under the NEB, we must have a critical stance toward its—hopefully oblivious—reproduction of the myths of universalism, of better living through technology, and of replicating modern/colonial power structures and its dynamics of coloniality. As Myriam Douo argues in her critique of the NEB: "Only by acknowledging that it is perpetuating colonial capitalism, and committing to ending this approach, can the EU's Green Deal be truly effective in addressing climate change."^{xlix}

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION: BRINGING THE CRITIQUES TO BOS

In this section, we explore what the critiques might mean to the BoS project. We shift again in scale, to that of a singular project with specific territorial and institutional constraints. In the previous sections, we found a range of issues that we are in danger of replicating under the name of the Bauhaus and the NEB frame:

- modern/colonial global power structures and the dynamics of coloniality,
- the modern/colonial myths of universalism,
- the modern/colonial myth of better living through technology.

When looking at BoS, there are more aspects to add. BoS deals specifically with two dimensions largely absent from the concerns of the Bauhaus and the NEB: water bodies and relations with more-than-humans. Among water bodies, the seas and oceans constitute a central connection between Europe and the rest of the world. This is especially relevant when we think of the structures and networks that gave Europe access to primary goods but also to a (mostly enslaved) labor force to build up its national, imperial, and corporate powers. Such structures and networks have allowed Eurocentric modernity to solidify, intensify, and expand. While the BoS approach to the seas is to look from the sea toward the continent, we may keep in mind historical traumatic relations with the oceans. On top of that, BoS focuses on regenerative relations with more-than-human entities. Engaging nonhuman entities in design is a growing field,¹ however, the same principle applies to this emerging approach: it is crucial to be aware of the perpetuation of extractive structures of colonialism or the myths of modernity when addressing other species and entities. The last item to add to this list is the need to have a critical view of water bodies and the historical (mostly extractive) relations made with and through these bodies of water.

4.1 Discussion: Outlining Questions in Search of an Ethics of Possibility

Bringing all the critiques to explore how BoS can progress toward an ethics of possibility,^{li} our goal is to pose questions to assist the critical awareness needed in our trajectory. We tackle the four issues highlighted in this review of critiques. In each category, we finish by outlining questions to serve as orientation points for an ethics of possibility. We hope the questions may also inspire others to reflect on how design (research) projects replicate oppressive structures, both present and inherited. We urge this section to be read as an example, not a recipe.

4.1.1 *The Danger of Blindly Replicating (Modern/Colonial) Global Power Structures and Its Dynamics of Coloniality*

The Bauhaus relied on the extraction of goods from the colonized world to enable the production model on which it was grounded and sustain the industrial-consumerist lifestyle as part of the mentality of Eurocentric modernity. Through coloniality, much of the constructs and structures that made Europe the center of the world at the expense of unmaking

other places and peoples remains. The dynamics of coloniality impose Euro-US-centric lifestyles and standards on the rest of the world. For the BoS project, we may have to be aware that the explorations and solutions may take advantage of these structures of coloniality and end up being imposed elsewhere, disrespecting local conditions. We must be critical of what kind of extractivism our testbeds may rely on and try to steer away from extractive relations. Furthermore, to avoid these experiences from being imposed as recipes created in Europe, we may have to highlight in every publication and communication that BoS is a situated project with pilot projects specific to each region that only serve as examples. In this case, each example may inspire action elsewhere but should not be seen as a universal solution. Questions we could ask here are: Are we creating or relying on extractive relations with others? Do our ideas rely on exploitative access to goods, materials, or other resources outside Europe? Is our project creating or replicating any exploitation of labor from underprivileged populations? Are our findings transmitted as global recipes? How do our experiments and solutions relate to the framing of ancestral and new lifestyles? How can we conduct and share our research in ways that do not impose solutions?

4.1.2 The Danger of Reinforcing the Myth of Universalism

Eurocentric modernity/coloniality came with a myth of posing everyone as equal and every place as the same. Although this had a reason to emerge, especially in the postwar scenarios, in practice, the treatment and power positions inscribed to different people and places were far from egalitarian. By promoting a discourse about Europe that does not break with such interpretations, the NEB fails to steer citizens toward a nuanced view of local differences, power structures, and oppressive relations in Europe and between the EU and the rest of the world. To counter this, we may benefit from presenting the BoS's efforts as local and situated explorations. We may sharpen how we see the project and the different regions involved as having specific cultures, identities, and needs. We may benefit from allowing different, even contradicting perspectives to emerge among the project partners. On a finer level, we may need to evaluate with nuance how we see and treat people in the project by acknowledging differences and trying to involve diverse communities as much as possible in equitable and reparatory manners that may invert problematic power relations. Questions relating to this could be: How and to whom is our project and its activities accessible? Are we replicating structures of privilege? How can we ensure that our view of local populations allows plural cultures and identities to flourish? How can our project allow diverse manifestations of design between the different regions in which it operates? How can we highlight the situatedness of our project, its materials, and its explorations? How can we repair problematic power relations concerning the people we invite to participate in the project?

4.1.3 The Danger of Replicating the Myth of Better Living through Technology

Eurocentric modernity/coloniality brought with it an idea that technological solutions were the path toward a better life, and the Bauhaus was at the forefront of creating new solutions in every scale ranging from the home to the city. However, this "better life" was not meant for all. Technological solutions benefited European elites and white elites in former colonies and forced the migration of poor populations within the European continent. Better living through technology has also been reliant on exploiting other places and peoples. As an initiative ostensibly aimed at sustainability, the NEB would benefit from countering the reliance on technological solutions grounded on the extraction of materials that cause environmental impact in Europe and abroad. Furthermore, we must be aware of who is privileged or oppressed or exploited by the technological solutions coming from our project, in terms of places and cultures inhabited by humans and more-than-humans. We can ask questions such as: Are our technology-based solutions the only way to solve problems? To whom are our technological solutions aimed? How can we design and research different

solutions for, by, and with different communities? How do technological solutions created in our project oppress or exploit others?

4.1.4 The Lack of a Critical View Towards Water Bodies and the Historical Relations Made with and through Them

To many non-European humans and more-than-human beings alike, the European way of connecting with and through water bodies generally represents trauma. Furthermore, Western extractive economies and lifestyles have exploited the seas and other water bodies; more-than-humans have not had a say in such exploitations. On the other hand, through the historical dynamics of colonization and how industrialization forced migration of poor Europeans to former colonies, Europe was never (and is even less so today) made up completely of Europeans.^{lii} A large population of immigrants is spread across its nations.^{liii} We must not forget how the current reality of the Mediterranean Sea as a deadly migrant route shows how different European countries have addressed this contemporary challenge, often in inhumane and opportunistic ways. Here we could ask questions such as: How can we deal with the traumatic history between Europe and the bodies of water for people and more-than-humans? Can we help flatten or invert unbalanced power relations in our processes instead of perpetuating them? How can our project help in raising new questions related to borders and occupation around bodies of water?

5 CONCLUSION

This article represents an effort to look back and understand where we find ourselves as part of a particular historical legacy, its structures, and myths. We outlined the critiques to the Bauhaus and the NEB. In search of a critical view that could help us act on the ethics of possibility,^{liv} we outlined what these critiques may mean for our project. In several topics in the discussion, we had overlapping issues related to power structures and extractive relations. Many of these aspects are manifestations of historical structures that remain in place. We recognize that our action is highly conditioned by such aspects, as well as the time limitations of BoS (2023–2025). From such an outline, we posed questions as orientation points for an ethics of possibility with hope of inspiring others to reflect on their own projects.^{lv}

In the BoS we inherit various problematic aspects from the Bauhaus and the NEB. Being aware of these structures and the dangers they bring to people, more-than-humans, cultures, and places in and outside Europe, we believe we are better off performing the design projects by being humble and honest about the structures in which we are located instead of assuming a blank slate approach. We conclude that it may be beneficial for achieving the ethics of possibility if we confess that we are under frames and inheritances infused with problematic relations and that our project has a limited scope and time span. We hope this article serves as an example of how we as designers (and researchers) can be both critical and humble about the past to explore openings for other, possible plural futures.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge Beatrice Maggipinto's contribution to some of the paper's illustrations. This work benefited from the collaboration of the ongoing Bauhaus of the Seas Sails EU-funded project through Grant agreement ID: 101079995. ITI/LARsyS is funded by FCT Project UIDB/50009/2020.

REFERENCES

-
- ⁱ New European Bauhaus, “Beautiful, Sustainable, Together,” https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en (accessed November 17, 2023).
- ⁱⁱ European Commission, Directorate General for Communication, *State of the Union 2020* (Publications Office, 2020), <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2775/27587>. In July 2023, the European Commission (EC) suggested making the NEB a new European funding mission; later in 2023, this proposal was denied, keeping the NEB as funding frame under cluster 2 of the EC’s higher-level funding mission. See more at <https://sciencebusiness.net/news/missions/no-more-new-european-bauhaus-mission>.
- ⁱⁱⁱ Three authors of this article are the original proponents of the Bauhaus of the Seas manifesto: Pestana, Duarte, and Nunes.
- ^{iv} Nuno Nunes, Mariana Pestana, Frederico Duarte, Miguel Figueira, José Albergaria, and Heitor Alvelos, “New European Bauhaus (NEB) Preamble” to “The Bauhaus of the Seas—A Manifesto for the New European Bauhaus,” *Design Issues* 40, no. 2 (Spring 2024): 90–97, https://doi.org/10.1162/desi_a_00758.
- ^v See <https://bauhaus-seas.eu>.
- ^{vi} Arjun Appadurai, *The Future as Cultural Fact: Essays on the Global Condition* (London: Verso, 2013).
- ^{vii} *Ibid.*, 295.
- ^{viii} *Ibid.*
- ^{ix} *Ibid.*, 299.
- ^x Daniel Christian Wahl, *Designing Regenerative Cultures* (Axminster, UK: Triarchy Press, 2016).
- ^{xi} Elizabeth Chin, “Bauhaus and the People without Design History,” in *Bauhaus Futures*, ed. Laura Forlano, Molly Wright Steenson, and Mike Ananny (Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2019), 85–94.
- ^{xii} Ramia Mazé, “Design Education Practice: Reflections on Feminist Modes and Politics,” in *Bauhaus Futures*, ed. Laura Forlano, Molly Wright Steenson, and Mike Ananny (Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2019), 3–24, <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12044.003.0013>.
- ^{xiii} Chin, “Bauhaus and the People.”
- ^{xiv} Renata Marques Leitão, “Recognizing and Overcoming the Myths of Modernity,” in *Design as a Catalyst for Change: DRS International Conference 2018*, ed. C. Storni, K. Leahy, M. McMahon, P. Lloyd, and E. Bohemia (Limerick Ireland, 2018), <https://doi.org/10.21606/drs.2018.468>.
- ^{xv} Elizabeth Tunstall, *Decolonizing Design: A Cultural Justice Guidebook* (Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2023), 58.
- ^{xvi} Aníbal Quijano, “Coloniality and Modernity/Rationality,” *Cultural Studies* 21, nos. 2–3 (March 2007): 168–78, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09502380601164353>; Walter Dignolo, *Local Histories/Global Designs: Coloniality, Subaltern Knowledges, and Border Thinking* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2012); Walter Dignolo, “Introduction: Coloniality of Power and De-Colonial Thinking,” *Cultural Studies* 21, nos. 2–3 (2007): 155–67, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09502380601162498>.
- ^{xvii} Enrique Dussel, “Europe, Modernity, and Eurocentrism,” *Nepantla: Views from South* 1, no. 3 (2000): 465–478.
- ^{xviii} Here we use the word *men* on purpose as women were not a direct part of the group that benefited from modernity. Modernity posed men as superior to women. Dussel, “Europe, Modernity, and Eurocentrism”; Leitão, “Recognizing and Overcoming the Myths of Modernity.”
- ^{xix} Hicham Khalidi and Rolando Vázquez, “A New Bauhaus? The Debate for a More Inclusive Europe,” *Rektoverso* (2021), <https://www.rektoverso.be/artikel/a-new-bauhaus-the-debate-for-a-more-inclusive-europe>.
- ^{xx} Dignolo, *Local Histories/Global Designs*.
- ^{xxi} Leitão, “Recognizing and Overcoming the Myths of Modernity.”
- ^{xxii} Khalidi and Vázquez, “A New Bauhaus?”; Leitão, “Recognizing and Overcoming the Myths of Modernity”; Tunstall, *Decolonizing Design*.
- ^{xxiii} Quijano, “Coloniality and Modernity/Rationality.”
- ^{xxiv} *Ibid.*
- ^{xxv} Khalidi and Vázquez, “A New Bauhaus?”

xxvi Rolando Vazquez, “Precedence, Earth and the Anthropocene: Decolonizing Design,” *Design Philosophy Papers* 15, no. 1 (January 2, 2017): 77–91, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14487136.2017.1303130>.

xxvii Ibid.; Tunstall, *Decolonizing Design*.

xxviii Tunstall, *Decolonizing Design*.

xxix Ibid., 47.

xxx Ibid.

xxxi The Van Eyck—Multiform Institute for Fine Art, Design, and Reflection is a postacademic institute for research and production in fine art, design, and art theory, based in Maastricht, Netherlands. The academy was established in 1948 and was named after painter Jan van Eyck.

xxxii “Letter to Object to the Term ‘New European Bauhaus’—Jan van Eyck,” <https://janvaneyck.nl/apply/letter-to-object-to-the-term-new-european-bauhaus/> (accessed November 17, 2023).

xxxiii Khalidi and Vázquez, “A New Bauhaus?”

xxxiv European Commission, “Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions,” 2021.

xxxv Tunstall, *Decolonizing Design*.

xxxvi Appadurai, *The Future as Cultural Fact*.

xxxvii European Commission, Directorate General for Communication, *State of the Union 2020*; European Commission, “Communication from the Commission”; New European Bauhaus, “NEB Compass” (European Commission, n.d.); European Commission, “Report on the Co-Design Phase—Annex to the Communication from the European Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions,” 2021.

xxxviii European Commission, “Communication from the Commission.”

xxxix European Commission, *State of the Union 2020*.

xl European Commission, “New European Bauhaus Compass V4,” 7.

xli Ibid., 8.

xlii Ibid., 9.

xliii Ibid.

xliv European Commission, “Communication from the Commission,” 7.

xlv European Commission, “Report on the Co-Design Phase,” 20.

xlvi European Commission, “Communication from the Commission,” 6.

xlvii Khalidi and Vázquez, “A New Bauhaus?”

xlviii Ibid.

xlix Myriam Douo, “Climate Colonialism and the EU’s Green Deal,” *Al Jazeera*, June 23, 2021, <https://www.aljazeera.com/opinions/2021/6/23/the-eus-green-deal-could-propagate-climate-colonialism>.

¹ See Rosi Braidotti, “Posthuman, All Too Human: Towards a New Process Ontology,” *Theory, Culture & Society* 23, nos. 7–8 (2006): 197–208, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263276406069232>; Paul Coulton and Joseph Galen Lindley, “More-Than Human Centred Design: Considering Other Things,” *Design Journal* 22, no. 4 (2019): 463–81, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14606925.2019.1614320>; María Puig de la Bellacasa, “‘Nothing Comes Without Its World’: Thinking with Care,” *Sociological Review* 60, no. 2 (2012): 197–216, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-954X.2012.02070.x>; Maria Puig de la Bellacasa, “Matters of Care in Technoscience: Assembling Neglected Things,” *Social Studies of Science* 41, no. 1 (2011): 85–106, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306312710380301>; Laura Forlano, “Posthumanism and Design,” *She Ji: The Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation* 3, no. 1 (2017): 16–29, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sheji.2017.08.001>; Laura Forlano, “Decentering the Human in the Design of Collaborative Cities,” *Design Issues* 32, no. 3 (Summer 2016): 42–54, https://doi.org/10.1162/DESI_a_00398; Ann Light, “In Dialogue with the More-than-Human: Affective Prefiguration in Encounters with Others,” *Interactions* 30, no. 4 (July 2023): 24–27, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3599956>.

² Appadurai, *The Future as Cultural Fact*.

ⁱⁱ Tunstall, *Decolonizing Design*.

ⁱⁱⁱ Khalidi and Vázquez, "A New Bauhaus?"

^{iv} Appadurai, *The Future as Cultural Fact*.

^v Ibid.

Pre publication draft